

Data Analysis of Mark Using SPSS

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Abstract— A student's life revolves around their grades. It is critical to know that we do not fall behind in our studies, particularly during the pandemic. The aim of this paper is to examine student grades and provide assistance to both students and teachers. With the help of the SPSS tool, which can be used for statistical analysis, we can perform data analysis of marks of the students. Using the results obtained, we can provide helpful insight to both teachers and students alike.

Keywords—Descriptive statistics, measure of central tendency, spss, data analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Improving students' academic performance is a difficult challenge for the higher education sector. Especially during the pandemic, it is important to know that students don't fall behind in their studies. Descriptive statistics are used to characterise the fundamental characteristics of a study's results. They offer fast summaries of the sample and the metrics.

Summaries made from the descriptive statistical analysis may be either quantitative, i.e. Summary statistics, or visual, i.e. Simple-to-understand graphs. These summaries may serve as the foundation for a more detailed interpretation of the data as part of a larger statistical study, or they may be adequate on their own. Statistics is the scientific method for gathering, organising, analysing, and interpreting data for the purposes of explanation and decision-making.

SPSS stands for Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The SPSS software platform offers advanced statistical analysis, a vast library of machine learning algorithms, text analysis, open source extensibility, integration with big data and seamless deployment into applications. SPSS helps to understand data, analyse trends, forecast and plan to validate assumptions etc.^[1] SPSS tool simplifies the process of the analysis the data and it is easy to draw conclusions from the analysis.

Some Fundamental Definitions

(a) Population - A population is a collection of people from which data will be obtained.

(b) Sample - A sample is subset of a population.

(c) Variable - A variable is a quality or quantity attribute of any member of a population that varies from one member to the next.

(d) Quantitative variable - A quantitative variable is one that differs in quantity.

(e) Qualitative variable - A qualitative variable or attribute is a variable that differs in consistency, such as colour or the degree of damage to a vehicle in an accident.

(f) Discrete variable - A discrete variable is one that has no value between two variables, such as the number of children in a family.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The process of analysing, cleansing, transforming, and modelling data with the aim of finding useful information, informing conclusions, and enhancing decision-making is known as data analysis. We conduct a data analysis of student grades for a specific academic year and draw conclusions from the findings. We use SPSS tool for conducting data analysis.

Descriptive statistics is a strong beast of burden as it gathers and summarises massive quantities of data and information in a manageable and structured manner; It is a relatively simple method that can easily translate into a frequency distribution, percentages, and overall averages.

The research result provides the evidence a practitioner needs to improve teaching and learning for the group and individuals within it. It also helps us to understand the weak points and can help to immensely improve the quality of education.

The study results could reveal how much time and effort a student put into the exam. By understanding the obtained results, the practitioner and the student will know which areas they should work on and how much more effort and time they should do to achieve the desired results.

There are a variety of tools that can be used to analysis the data. Previous research has also revealed that the results reported by may have slight changes. The performance of these tools may vary. SPSS is preferred as it is easy to use and can be easy understand.

III. METHODOLOGY

From 30 student population, a sample of 15 students are taken

Cases	Marks (out of 50)
1	45.0
2	33.0
3	29.5
4	44.0
5	33.0

6	27.0
7	44.0
8	45.0
9	47.0
10	29.5
11	34.0
12	33.0
13	27.0
14	44.0
15	20.0

IV. RESULTING STEPS

- 1)Open IBM SPSS software. If not present, install SPSS tool.
- 2)Either open the sample data or add the sample data.
- 3)Open **Analysis > Descriptive analysis > Descriptive.**

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
scores	30	15.0	47.0	34.067	8.4146

- 4) Open **Analysis > Descriptive analysis > Frequencies.**

Frequencies

Statistics		
scores		
N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Mean		34.067
Median		33.000
Mode		33.0
Std. Deviation		8.4146
Variance		70.806

- 5)Open **Graphs > Chart builder**

A. Installation of spss

- Go to SPSS software website.
- Sign up.
- Install SPSS software.
- Create the sample data

B. Descriptive analysis

- Open Analysis > Descriptive analysis > Descriptive.
- Open Analysis > Descriptive analysis > Frequencies.
- Open Graphs > Chart builder.

V. CONCLUSION

With the help of the obtained data conclusion, we can provide appropriate steps to assist students in improving their grades. By analysing students' performance with the help of SPSS tool, we will be able to obtain information to improve both tests and instruction, to determine grades or the passing score on the test, to determine whether the test was too easy or too hard, and to evaluate the effectiveness of instruction.

VI. FUTURE WORK

It's possible that any updates might be made to make it more user-friendly. The reporting format has little production, is cluttered, and takes a long time to complete. If they could have a marketplace to add extra features to the tool, that would be great. The application's automated risk tests must be streamlined and varied.

VII. REFERENCE

- [1] <https://www.ibm.com/products/spss-statistics>
- [2] IJRITCC Data analysis of student marks with descriptive statistics
- [3] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/spss-statistics>